

EFFECTS OF BOILED UNRIPE PLANTAIN (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') PEEL FLOUR ON LAYING PERFORMANCE, HAEMATOLOGY AND PRODUCTION ECONOMICS OF ISA BROWN LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to evaluate the effects of diets containing Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour (BUPPF) on laying performance, haematology, and production economics of Isa Brown layers. One hundred and fifty-six 18-week-old ISA Brown laying hens were randomly divided into 3 dietary treatments, with 4 replicates per treatment consisting of 13 birds per replicate in a completely randomized design. Diets contain 0% (control), 10% (T1) and 20% (T2) BUPPF as a replacement for maize offal. The hens were fed ad libitum experimental diets and water for six weeks. Data were collected on Egg Weight, egg mass, Hen Day Egg Production, Average Feed Intake (AFI), Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR), Packed Cell Volume (PCV), Haemoglobin, Red Blood Cell (HRBC), White Blood Cell (WBC), platelets, lymphocytes, heterophils, monocytes, eosinophils, basophils, ingredient cost, feed cost, revenue, gross margin, efficiency of egg production and benefits cost ratio of laying hens fed experimental diets. All data collected were analysed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results showed that laying hens fed BUPPF diets (T1 and T2) had significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher AFI (103.8g; 98.28g) than those fed control diet (89.18g). Laying hens fed control diet had significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) white blood cells count (15.88×10^9 cells/L) and ingredients cost (159.66N/kg) than those fed BUPPF diets (14.13×10^9 cells/L; 14.17×10^9 cells/L and 155.66N/kg; 151.66N/kg). Conclusively, BUPPF diets improved AFI and reduced the ingredient cost of laying hens. Therefore, boiled unripe plantain peel flour can be included up to 20% in the diets of laying hens without deleterious effect on the hens.

Keywords: Boiled unripe plantain peel flour, laying hens, haematology and production economics.

INTRODUCTION

Poultry production has not been a lucrative enterprise because of the high cost of conventional feedstuffs. Feed cost accounts for between 65 - 70% of the total cost of production (Maina *et al.*, 2012) and is a major factor that determines the viability and profitability of poultry farming enterprise. However, research efforts are being directed towards the use of alternative feed resources that are less competed for by humans, readily available and cheap (Ibitoye *et al.*, 2010). One of such alternatives is plantain peel.

Plantain peel poses to be a potential source of nutrients for animal feed production and its use for this purpose should be encouraged, as this will help to reduce the menace of plantain waste in the environment (Okareh *et al.*, 2015) and also decrease the cost of production. However, the use of plantain peel in poultry feed has been limited because of possible deleterious effects arising from the presence of tannins (Blandon *et al.*, 2015) and its fibrousness (Ezieshi and Olomu, 2004). Adeniji *et al.* (2008) reported that the tannin levels found in both plantain and banana peel is high in concentrations and thus could be toxic; however, processing should be carefully carried out to reduce their levels in the peels prior to utilization.

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) peel has been treated for poultry use to remove or lower the anti-nutritional factors, using different processing or treatment techniques like lye water (Williams and Williams, 1982), 15 minutes lye water treatment (Akande and Agbetuyi, 2019), sun-drying (Akinsanmi *et al.*, 2015; Akande and Agbetuyi, 2019), autoclaving at 121°C for fifteen (15) minutes and then inoculating it with fungi (Lawal *et al.*, 2012). Patterson *et al.* (2017)

reported that boiling or cooking greatly improved the nutritional value of foods by reducing their anti-nutritional (e.g., tannins and trypsin inhibitors) contents. Blandon *et al.* (2015) reported that tannin content in dried banana peel reduces from 1.2g/100g to 1.04, 0.59 and 0.46 g/100g by autoclaving, oven heating and soaking in boiling water, respectively. Tannin contents in African Elim (*Canarium schweinfurthii*) fruit reduce from 18.09mg/g to 3.65mg/g after boiling in water at 100°C for 20 minutes (Orisa *et al.*, 2024). Hence, it is postulated that plantain peel should be treated by boiling before its inclusion in laying hen's diet.

Blood is an important index of physiological, pathological and nutritional status in an organism (Olorode *et al.*, 2007). There is limited information on the use of plantain peel in the diets of laying hens. This study, therefore, evaluates the effects of boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets on laying performance, haematology and production economics of Isa brown layers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site of the Experiment

The experiment was conducted at the Layer Unit, Teaching and Research Farm of Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Source and processing of Unripe Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') Peels

Unripe plantain peels were sourced from a plantain chips processing enterprise in Ogbomoso, Oyo State. The peels were boiled at 100°C for forty (40) minutes in a cooking pot and sun-dried to a constant weight (when they became crispy) at a moisture content of 9.37%. The dried peels were ground using a hammer mill with sieve

size of 0.5mm to reduce the particle size to obtain Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour (BUPPF). The BBUPPF was stored in air tight container at room temperature prior to its inclusion in the experimental diets.

Management of Experimental Birds and Diets

One hundred and fifty-six 18-week-old pullets of Isa Brown strain of layers were used for the experiment. The grower birds were purchased at 12 weeks of age from a reputable farm, fed grower mash feed for 6 weeks until they reached sexual maturity and attain 20% egg production before being fed experimental diets. At 18 weeks of age, the birds were randomly divided into three

(3) dietary treatment groups of 4 replicates with 13 birds in each replicate and 52 birds per treatment in a completely randomized design experiment. The experimental birds were kept in two-tiers battery cage system for a period of 6 weeks of the study. Feed and water were offered *ad libitum* to the birds. Routine management practices and vaccination programme were administered as due. Three experimental diets were formulated for the study with BUPPF replacing. Maize offal. Diets contained 0%, 10% and 20% boiled unripe plantain peel flour in Control, T1 and T2, respectively (Table1). The diets were formulated to meet the standard nutritional requirements of laying hens.

Table 1: Gross Composition of the Experimental Layer Diets

Ingredients	Control (0%BUPPF)	T1 (10% BUPPF)	T2 (20% BUPPF)
Maize	44.30	44.30	44.30
Maize offal	20.00	10.00	-
BUPPF	-	10.00	20.00
Wheat offal	-	-	-
Soybean meal	22.00	22.00	22.00
FM (72% CP)	3.00	4.00	4.00
Methionine	0.20	0.20	0.20
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25
Vit-Premix **	0.25	0.25	0.25
Bonemeal	3.00	3.00	3.00
Limestone	7.00	7.00	7.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Determined Analysis

(%) *

Crude Protein *	16.90	17.05	17.35
Ether Extract*	8.10	8.30	8.10
Crude Fibre*	6.30	5.80	6.50
ME (kcal/kg))	3020.90	3040.88	3014.48
Phosphorous	0.64	0.69	0.74
Calcium	3.73	4.49	5.26
Lysine	0.91	0.89	0.86
Methionine	0.50	0.48	0.46

**Vit-Premix supplied the following per kg of the diet 10,000IU vitamin A, 2,000IU vitamin D₃, 23mg vitamin E, 2mg vitamin K₃, 3mg vitamin B₁, 6mg vitamin B₂, 50mg Niacin, 10mg calcium Pantothenate, 5mg vitamin B₆, 0.025mg vitamin B₁₂, 1mg Folic acid, 0.05mg Biotin, 400mg choline chloride, 120mg manganese, 100mg Iron, 80mg zinc, 8.5mg copper, 1.5mg Iodine, 0.3mg cobalt, 0.12mg selenium, 120mg antioxidant

Note: BUPPF= Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour, FM= Fish Meal, * =Parameters of determined nutrients
ME= Metabolizable energy was calculated using Pauzenga equation,

Data Collection

Proximate composition of Boiled unripe plantain peel flour and maize offal

The proximate composition (dry matter, crude protein, crude fibre, ether extract, and ash) of boiled unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') peel flour and maize offal was determined according to the method of AOAC (2012). The metabolizable energy was calculated via Pausenga equation (Pausenga, 1985) while the nitrogen-free extract was calculated using the proximate composition of the peels and maize offal

Anti-nutritional composition of raw and boiled unripe plantain peel flour

Samples of raw and boiled unripe plantain peel flour were sent to the laboratory for phytochemical analysis of the tannin, phytate, oxalates and saponin according to the methods of Beutler *et al.* (1980), AOAC (2012), Alavi and West (1983) and Okwu and Josiah (2006), respectively.

Laying Performance of the Experimental Birds

i. Hen Day Egg Production (HDEP): During the study, daily egg production was monitored. Hen day egg production was calculated with the formula:

$$\text{Hen Day Egg Production} = \frac{\text{Number of eggs laid} \times 100}{\text{Number of hens} \times \text{Number of days}}$$

ii. Average Feed Intake (AFI) was calculated by dividing the total feed intake by the total number of birds per replicate.

iii. Average Egg Weight (AEW): Eggs were weighed daily. This was calculated by dividing the total weight of eggs laid by the number of eggs.

iv. Egg mass: This was calculated by multiplying the AEW by the hen day egg production

v. Feed conversion ratio: This was calculated by dividing the average feed intake by the average egg mass

Blood Sample Collection and Analysis

On the 37th day of the experiment, blood samples were collected very early in the morning before feeding them, from the wing vein of 8 birds randomly selected per treatment. Collected samples were transferred into sample bottles containing Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic acid (EDTA) for haematological parameters determination at the Chemical Pathology Laboratory. The haematological parameters that were determined include: Red Blood Cells (RBC) count, White Blood Cells (WBC) count and the differentials (monocytes, lymphocytes, heterophils, basophils and eosinophils), Packed Cells Volume (PCV), haemoglobin concentration (Hb) and platelets (Plt) count. The haemoglobin concentration was measured by cyan methaemoglobin method, red and white blood cells count were determined using improved Neubauer haemocytometer methods as described by Jain (1986). PCV was determined using the micro-haematocrit method described by Dacie and Lewis (1999).

Production Economics Analysis

The production economics of laying hens fed BUPPF diets were calculated as follows:

i. Ingredient cost (₦/kg feed) = Total ingredients cost per kg.

ii. Feed cost (₦/kg) = Total feed consumed x Cost per kg of feed

iii. Revenue (₦/crate of egg) = Total number of eggs x Market Price of egg

iv Gross Margin (₦/kg) = Revenue from egg ((₦/crates of egg)– Total Feed Cost (₦/kg)

v Efficiency of Egg Production (%) =
$$\frac{\text{Egg Mass (g)} \times 100}{\text{Feed Intake}}$$

vi Benefit Cost Ratio =
$$\frac{\text{Revenue}}{\text{Feed Cost}}$$

Statistical Analysis

All data collected were subjected to one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SAS (2004) Software Package, Duncan's option of the same software was used to separate the means. The probability of 5% was considered significant ($P \leq 0.05$).

Model

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + T_i + e_{ij}$$

NOTE: Y_{ij} = Response variable (e. g. laying performance, haematology and cost-benefits)

μ = overall population mean,

e_{ij} = Experimental error,

T_i = effect of the i^{th} treatment (diet with boiled unripe plantain peel inclusion levels)

RESULTS

The proximate composition of boiled unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') peel flour and maize offal is shown in Table 2. The 91.63% dry matter, 7.38% crude protein, 5.45% crude fibre and 3298.23kcal/kg metabolizable energy

obtained in boiled unripe plantain peel flour was slightly lower than 95.04% dry matter, 8.82% crude protein, 8.42% crude fibre and 3300.90kcal/kg metabolizable energy of maize offal. However similar values of ash (5.05% and 4.33%) and nitrogen-free extract (64.80% and 64.43%) were obtained in boiled unripe plantain peel flour and maize offal.

The results of anti-nutritional contents in raw and boiled unripe plantain peel flour presented on Table 3 shows that there was a reduction in the tannin content of the peels from 292.67mg/100g in the raw peels to 235.56mg/100g in boiled peels. However, the phytate, oxalate and saponin contents of the peels were similar in raw and boiled peels.

The laying performance of Isa brown layers fed boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets is presented in Table 4. The dietary treatment had significant effect on the average feed intake ($P < 0.05$) of the hens. Laying hens fed BUPPF diets had significantly higher average feed intake ($P < 0.05$) than those fed control diet. However, there were no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in the egg weight, egg mass, hen day egg production and feed conversion ratio of the experimental hens.

Table 2: Proximate composition of boiled unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava' peel flour and maize offal

Parameters	Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour	Maize offal
Dry matter (%)	91.63±0.31	95.04±0.33
Cr Crude protein (%)	7.38±0.02	8.82±0.61
Ash (%)	5.05±0.04	4.33±0.39
Ether Extract (%)	8.95±0.04	7.25±1.48
Crude fibre (%)	5.45±0.04	8.42±0.19
Nitrogen Free Extract (%)	64.80±0.36	64.43±0.08
Metabolizable Energy (kcal/kg)	3298.23±8.98	3300.90±11.1

Note: Three samples per treatment were used for the chemical analysis.

The haematological parameters of Isa brown layers fed boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets are presented in Table 5. There were no significant ($p>0.05$) differences in the haematological parameters examined except for white

blood cells. Laying hens fed control diet had significantly ($P<0.05$) higher white blood cells count (15.88×10^9 cells/L) than those fed boiled unripe plantain diets (14.13×10^9 cells/L and 14.17×10^9 cells/L)

Table 3: Anti-nutritional contents in raw and boiled unripe plantain peel flour

Samples	Tannin (mg/100g)	Phytate (mg/100g)	Oxalate (mg/100g)	Saponin (mg/100g)
Raw Unripe Plantain Peel Flour	292.567±0.82	163.36±1.22	21.91±0.20	3.81±0.04
Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour	239.56±0.82	159.76±0.41	25.4±0.02	4.2±0.04

Table 4: Laying Performance of Isa Brown layers fed boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets

Parameters	Control (0%BUPPF)	T1 (10%BUPPF)	T2 (20%BUPPF)	P-value	±SEM
Egg W (g)	48.26	46.51	45.85	0.219	0.93
Egg Mass (g)	27.65	29.14	23.85	0.39	2.71
HDEP (%)	57.29	62.66	52.01	0.326	4.72
AFI (g/hen)	89.18 ^b	103.80 ^a	98.28 ^a	0.001	1.82
FCR	3.24	3.63	4.28	0.099	0.33

^{a,b} : Means along the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P \leq 0.050$)

Note: BUPPF=Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour, HDEP= Hen Day Egg Production

AFI =Average Feed Intak; Egg W= Egg weight SEM= Standard Error of Mean

Table 5: Haematological parameters of Isa Brown layers fed boiled unripe plantain Peel flour diets

Parameters	Control	T1 (10%BUPPF)	T2 (20%BUPPF)	P- Value	±SEM
PCV (%)	25.88	22.63	23.00	0.168	1.27
Haemoglobin (g/dl)	8.46	7.41	7.56	0.195	0.43
RBC ($\times 10^{12}$ /L)	2.55	1.85	1.86	0.085	0.24
WBC ($\times 10^9$ cells/L)	15.88 ^a	14.13 ^b	14.17 ^b	0.009	0.41
Platelets ($\times 10^9$ cells/L)	129375	125000	115760	0.253	0.57
Lymphocytes (%)	60.38	56.25	56.50	0.281	1.99
Heterophils (%)	33.63	36.13	36.38	0.519	1.85
Monocytes (%)	3.13	3.13	3.00	0.957	0.34
Eosinophils (%)	3.88	3.63	3.88	0.948	0.63
Basophils (%)	0.25	0.13	0.25	0.800	0.15

^{a,b} : Means along the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

Note: BUPPF=Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel, PCV=Packed Volume, Cell

RBC=Red Blood Cell, WBC=White Blood Cell, SEM= Standard Error of Mean

The production economics of Isa brown layers fed boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets is presented in Table 5. There was a significant effect on the ingredient cost ($P < 0.05$) of the experimental diets. The highest ingredients cost (₦159.66/kg) was observed in the control diet while lowest cost was noticed in 20% BUPPF diet (₦151.66/kg). BUPPF reduces the cost of ingredients used in the formulation of the

experimental diets. However, there were no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in the feed cost, revenue, gross margin, efficiency of egg production and cost-benefit ratio of hens fed experimental diets. Numerical increases were recorded from the revenue and gross margin generated from the eggs laid by hens fed BUPPF diets when compared to the control.

Table 6: Production Economics of Isa Brown layers fed BUPPF diets

Parameters	Control (10%BUPPF)	T1 (10%BUPPF)	T2 (20%BUPPF)	P-Value	±SEM
Ingredient Cost (₦/kg)	159.66 ^a	155.66 ^b	151.66 ^c	<0.0001	0.72
Feed Cost (₦/kg)	519.37	565.73	647.06	0.186	45.29
Revenue (₦/kg egg)	555.53	571.61	582.25	0.382	12.99
Gross Margin (₦/kg egg)	36.17	53.30	37.96	0.553	11.84
EEP (%)	31.00	28.07	24.27	0.505	2.41
Benefits-Cost Ratio	11.07	1.01	0.90	0.21	0.29

^{a, b, c}: Means along the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

Note: BUPPF=Boiled Unripe Plantain Peel Flour, EEP=Efficiency of Egg Production
SEM= Standard Error of Mean

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that there is slight variation in the nutritional composition of boiled unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') peel flour and maize offal. BUPPF contains slightly lower dry matter, crude protein, crude fibre and metabolizable energy compared to maize offal. These compositional differences have important nutritional and economic implications when BUPPF is used as a replacement ingredient for maize offal in diets of Isa brown hens. The slightly lower metabolizable energy value observed in BUPPF (3298.23±8.98kcal/kg) relative to maize offal (3300.90±11.1kcal/kg) is particularly important as energy intake is the primary

regulator of feed consumption in laying hens (Leeson and Summer, 2005). This suggests that laying hens fed BUPPF diets tend to increase feed intake to compensate for reduced dietary energy density. The values of metabolizable energy (3298.23±8.98kcal/kg) of boiled unripe plantain peel flour obtained in this study is similar to the 3295±0.50kcal/kg metabolizable energy reported by Arogbodo *et al.* (2021) but higher than 1850kcal/kg Metabolizable energy reported by Akande and Agbetuyi (2019) for sundried unripe plantain peel. The 5.45±0.04% value of crude fibre in BUPPF in this experiment is higher than 0.21±0.01% and 0.74% respectively reported by Arogbodo *et al.* (2021) and Akinsanmi *et*

al. (2015) for sundried unripe plantain peel. The $7.38 \pm 0.02\%$ of crude protein of BUPPF in the present study agreed with 7.89% crude protein reported by Akinsanmi *et al.* (2015) but disagreed with the range of $9.63\text{--}13.80\%$ reported by other authors (Oyedemi *et al.*, 2015; Arogbodo *et al.*, 2024; Akande *et al.*, 2019 and Arogbodo *et al.*, 2021) for sundried unripe plantain peel. The ash content in BUPPF ($5.05 \pm 0.04\%$) is similar to 4.30% ash content in sundried unripe plantain peel flour reported by Arogbodo *et al.* (2024) but lower than $17.28 \pm 0.15\%$, 17.50% and 17.211% ash content of sundried unripe plantain peel reported by Arogbodo *et al.* (2021), Oyedemi *et al.* (2015) and Akinsanmi *et al.* (2015) respectively. The variations observed in the proximate composition of boiled unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') peel flour in the present study and that of sundried unripe plantain peel (*Musa paradisiaca*) by earlier authors may have been due to differences in the processing methods, cultivars and geographical locations of the plantain plant when grown.

The decrease observed in the tannin content of boiled unripe plantain peel flour from $292.67\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ (raw) to $235.56\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ (boiled) may be due to loss of tannin in water during boiling. This seems to suggest that boiling of raw plantain peel in water at 100°C for 40 minutes enhanced the reduction in tannin content of boiled unripe plantain peel. Blandon *et al.* (2015) reported that tannin content in dried banana peel reduces from $1.2\text{g}/100\text{g}$ to $0.46\text{g}/100\text{g}$ after soaking in boiling water. Orisa *et al.* (2024) also reported reduction in tannin content of African Elim (*C. schweinfurthii*) fruit from $18.09\text{mg}/\text{g}$ to $3.65\text{mg}/\text{g}$ after boiling in water at 100°C for 20 minutes. The similarities observed in the phytate,

oxalate and saponin contents of raw and boiled unripe plantain peel flour despite boiling in this study could indicate that boiling does not have any effect on these anti-nutrients in plantain peel. However, Orisa *et al.* (2024) observed a reduction in oxalates content of raw African Elim fruit from $8.07\text{mg}/\text{kg}$ to $2.22\text{mg}/\text{kg}$ after boiling in water at 100°C for 20 minutes. It has also been reported that phytate content in raw African Elim fruit decreases from $429\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ to $125.30\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ after boiling in water at 100°C for 20 minutes (Orisa *et al.*, 2024).

The increased average daily intake recorded in hens fed BUPPF diet in the present study may be due to the palatability of the diet. This could be attributed to high vitamin C content in unripe plantain peel flour. It has been reported that unripe plantain peel contains $11.72\text{mg}/100\text{g}$ of vitamin C (Akinsanmi *et al.*, 2015) which might have enhanced the palatability of the diet. Abudabos *et al.* (2019) reported that the inclusion of vitamin C as much as $200\text{mg}/\text{L}$ in broiler ration when the environment's temperature is 32°C showed an increase in feed consumption of broiler up to 0.98% .

However, the higher AFI of laying hens fed BUPPF diets did not improve egg production of the hens. This could indicate that the hens could utilize the maize offal better than the peel. The increase observed in the average feed intake of laying hens fed the BUPPF diet in this study could also be attributed to the slight decrease recorded in the metabolizable energy of BUPPF relative to maize offal in the diet. Hens consume to satisfy their energy requirements. Diarra *et al.* (2020) also observed an increase in feed intake of laying hens fed diets supplemented with

papaya peel meal, which did not reflect on egg production of the hens. The authors attributed the increase in feed intake to enhanced palatability by vitamins and antioxidants provided by papaya peel meal. Several authors found non-significant differences in the feed intake of broiler chickens fed plantain peel diets. Oyedeji *et al.* (2015) noticed that there was no significant difference in the feed intake of broiler chickens fed ripe and unripe plantain peel. Akande and Agbetuyi (2019) observed that feed intake declined by about 35% in broilers fed sun-dried plantain peels, and by 20% for lye treatment and enzyme-supplemented plantain peel diets. Ogunsipe and Agbede (2010) stated that the feed intake decreased marginally with increased levels of plantain peels in the diet of rabbits. The differences observed in the feed intake of the experimental animals in the present study and those of earlier authors could be due to differences in processing method of plantain peels, cultivars and the animals used for the study.

The non-significant differences observed in the egg weight, egg mass, hen day egg production and feed conversion in this study shows that BUPPF could completely replace maize offal in the diet of laying hens without any adverse effect on the laying performance of the hens. The nutritional quality of BUPPF seems to be similar to that of maize offal due to the similarities observed in the egg weight, hen day egg production and feed conversion of the hens fed BUPPF diets and the control. Adrizal *et al.* (2021) reported that there were no significant differences in the egg weight, hen day egg production and feed conversion ratio of laying hens fed fermented pineapple waste.

Blood parameters are indispensable bio-tools for ascertaining the wellness of animals (Arogbodo *et al.*, 2024). The replacement of maize offal with BUPPF in the diet of laying hens in the present study seems to slightly reduce the white blood cell count of the hens. This could be attributed to the effect of residual anti-nutritional factors in the peels. However, the white blood cell counts of hens fed BUPPF diets in the present study was within the normal range for broiler chickens reported by Talebi *et al.* (2005). This suggests that BUPPF diet does not have any deleterious effect on the health status of laying hens. Duwa *et al.* (2014) observed reductions in the white blood cell of broilers chickens fed 10% banana peel meal. Oyewole *et al.* (2018) reported that laying hens fed 20% sweet orange peel meal had higher WBC than those fed other dietary treatment. The non-significant difference observed in the PCV, haemoglobin, RBC and their differentials in laying hens fed boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets and control diets shows that these blood parameters were not adversely affected by the dietary treatments. This result fell in line with the report of Arogbodo *et al.* (2024) who observed no significant difference in the PCV, haemoglobin, RBC, lymphocytes heterophils, eosinophils and basophils of broiler chickens fed unripe plantain peel diets.

BUPPF reduced the cost of ingredients used in the formulation of the experimental diets. The reduction recorded in the cost of ingredients for the formulated experimental diet when BUPPF was used to replace maize offal was an indication that BUPPF (alternative feed ingredient) was cheaper than maize offal (conventional feed

ingredient). Although there were no significant differences in the feed cost, profit, income and efficiency of egg production, there was a numerical difference in this result. Feeding BUPPF diet to laying hens tends to be better and more economical with greater profit than those fed control diet. Ogunsipe and Agbede (2010) observed that there was a decrease in the cost of feed when plantain peel was used to replace maize in rabbit diet. Blandon *et al.* (2015) noticed that increasing the replacement level of banana peels resulted in a lower feed cost of the diets in a study on effect of partial replacement of yellow corn by banana peels with and without enzymes on broiler's performance and blood parameters. Also, Abel *et al.* (2014) reported that feed cost per kilogram gain decreases significantly when treated banana peel meal was used to replace yellow maize in broiler diet. Several authors (Onu *et al.*, 2011 and Kalio *et al.*, 2013) had also observed similar trend with various by-products used in broilers'

diet. The variation recorded in the current study and the result of other authors could be due to the processing method of plantain peel flour used (boiled or not boiled), type of animal and varieties of plantain peel used for the study.

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, feeding boiled unripe plantain peel flour diets improved average daily feed intake and reduced the cost of the diets. Boiled unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') peel flour can therefore be included up to 20% in the diets of laying hens without deleterious effect on the laying performance, haematology and production economics of the hens. Other processing methods such as fermentation and enzyme supplementation are hereby recommended for optimal use of unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* cv. 'Cadava') peel flour in the diets of laying hens for improved performance, better haematology and production economics of the hens.

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